

KINETICS OF OXIDATION OF SOIL ORGANIC MATTER. PART I. RELATIVE ORDERS OF OXIDATION WITH SOME CHEMICAL REAGENTS

BY S. P. ROYCHOUDHURI AND A. B. BHUIYAN

The relative order of the rates of oxidation of soil organic matter of several soil samples and of Merck's humic acid have been carried out with (a) alkaline and acid potassium permanganate solutions and (b) acid potassium dichromate solution. The relative order with all the samples by these oxidants are similar.

The oxidation of soil organic matter may be effected by chemical reagents like acid and alkaline potassium permanganate, acid potassium dichromate and hydrogen peroxide. The oxidation of solid by a liquid oxidant is a case of heterogeneous reaction and, therefore, the theoretical considerations of homogeneous reactions are inapplicable to such cases. If, however, there be any inherent difference in the nature of the organic matter, it will be brought out in oxidation curves.

Robinson (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1927, 34, 339), Wakemnn and Stevens (*Soil Sci.*, 1930, 30, 97) and others have treated soils with varying concentrations of hydrogen peroxide to determine their humus contents. Esh and Guha-Sircar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 405) have studied the conditions under which soil humus can most easily be oxidised by hydrogen peroxide. In our present experiments, however, hydrogen peroxide was found not to be a suitable oxidising reagent for measuring the rate of oxidation of the organic matter, since it is easily decomposed by the walls of the containing vessel and by the powdered materials of the soil. Under such conditions, although by blank experiments, some correction of the disturbances due to the solid particles may be effected, any quantitative conclusions drawn from those data on the nature of the organic matter of the soil, will not be beyond criticism. Besides, the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide itself will be considerably affected by slight changes of temperature.

In the present paper, the rates of oxidation of the organic matter of eight top soil samples by the following chemical reagents have been determined: (i) alkaline potassium permanganate solution (0.1052 *N*), (ii) acid potassium permanganate solution (0.1052 *N*) and (iii) acid potassium dichromate solution (0.111 *N*).

These studies were also carried out with Merck's humic acid and with Dacca soil in which no manure was added, and the same soil treatment with green manure alone, and after combined treatments with green manure and lime, as also with green manure and lime and bone dust.

EXPERIMENTAL

Organic carbon in the soils was determined by following the rapid titration procedure advised by Walkley (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1935, 25, 598) and total nitrogen of the samples were determined by Kjeldahl's method. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I.
Percentages of organic carbon in the samples.

Substance.	Locality.	Organic carbon.	Nitrogen.	C/N ratio.
Dacca soil + no manure *	Dacca	0.63%	0.0501	12.60
Dacca soil + green manure *	..	1.50	0.057	26.31
Dacca soil + green manure + lime *	..	0.60	0.056	10.71
Dacca soil + green manure + lime + bone dust *	..	1.30	0.060	20.66
Soil No. 24A **	Raipur C. P.	0.714	0.0602	11.9
.. .. 30A **	Teliparamba Madras	5.68	0.35	16.02
.. .. 34A **	Calicut Madras	1.653	0.146	11.32
.. .. 64 **	Tenasserim Burma	2.857	0.166	17.2
.. .. 80 **	Satgaon Assam	1.418	0.13	10.09
.. .. 98A **	North Haji, Dacca Farm	0.99	0.087	11.38
.. .. 184 P **	Coimbatore	0.810	0.055	14.72
.. .. 186 P **	Coimbatore	0.410	0.040	10.25
Humic acid (Merck's)	...	43.0	2.94	14.62

* These samples were kindly supplied by Dr. S. S. Guha-Sircar.

** Laboratory Number.

Rates of the Oxidation.

The soils were finely powdered and passed through a 100 mesh sieve. Calculated quantities of soils containing 0.02g. of organic carbon were taken in 150 c. c. stoppered glass bottles and mixed with 100 c. c. of the oxidising reagents at a known instant of time. The bottles were then fixed to the clamps on the disc rotating inside a thermostat (25±0.2°). The exact time at which the contents of each of the bottles were mixed were noted. At suitable intervals of time the bottles were, in order, released from the clamps and placed for settling on a stand immersed in the water of the thermostat. At known instants of time, the clear supernatant liquids were pipetted out of the bottles and the amounts of oxidants present in the filtrates were determined by titrating with a suitable titrating liquid. In the case of alkaline potassium permanganate solution, the precipitated manganese dioxide was effectively removed by filtering the pipetted solution through a No. 3 sintered glass filter.

The oxidation curves with one of the three oxidising agents are shown in Fig. 1, while Table II summarises the relative orders of oxidation. The relative orders of the percentage of organic matter in different samples (*cf.* Table I) were also included in the same table.

FIG. 1.

Oxidation with acid $KMnO_4$

TABLE II.

Order of oxidation.

Alkaline KMnO_4 .	Acid KMnO_4 .	Acid $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.	Percentage of organic matter in different samples.
Humic acid > 30A > 64 > 24A > 80 > 98A > green manure + lime (Dacca soil) > 34A > no manure (Dacca soil) > 186 P > 184 P > green manure + lime + bone (Dacca soil) > green manure (Dacca soil).	Humic acid > 30A > 64 > 184 P > 80 > 24A > 34A > green manure + lime (Dacca soil) > 98A > no manure (Dacca soil) > 186 P > green manure + lime + bone (Dacca soil) > green manure (Dacca soil).	Humic acid > 30A > 64 > 24A > 98A > green manure + lime (Dacca soil) > no manure (Dacca soil) > 186 P > 80 > 184 P > 24A > green manure + lime + bone (Dacca soil) > green manure (Dacca soil).	Humic acid > 30A > 64 > 34A > green manure (Dacca soil) > 80 > green manure + lime + bone (Dacca soil) > 98A > 184P > 24A > no manure (Dacca soil) > green manure + lime (Dacca soil) > 186 P.

The rates of oxidation of the samples by three reagents are similar. This order is also more or less similar to that organic matter contents of the soils when we leave out the green manuring treatments. The results indicate that, at least partially, the ratios of soil solutions are determining the rates of oxidation of organic matters in soils, as the soils taken in these experiments are in inverse proportion to their organic carbon contents.

It was found that in the initial stages the rate of oxidation of the organic carbon of the soil, which is quite high, gradually decreases with time and after about six hours the amount of organic carbon oxidised reaches a maximum value. With humic acid it was found that after about two to three hours, the amount oxidised by the chemical reagents reaches a maximum value and that acid potassium permanganate oxidises it to a much greater extent than any of the other two chemical reagents. It was found that although the amount of humic acid used in these experiments contained 20 mg. of organic carbon, the actual amounts of organic carbon oxidised vary from 0.5 mg. to 12 mg. This suggests, therefore, that Merck's humic acid consists mostly of highly resistant type of organic matter. The same is true with the organic matter of soils.

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. S. S. Guha-Sircar for his kind criticisms in writing this paper.

Received June 18, 1942.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY,
DACCA.

